

Categoria A

REVISTA ARHEOLOGICĂ

serie nouă _ vol. XIX _ nr. 1

Indexată în bazele de date:

SCOPUS, ERIH PLUS, DOAJ, CEEOL, ROAD, ISIFI, CiteFactor

CHIȘINĂU 2023

ISSN 1857-016X
E-ISSN 2537-6144

INSTITUTUL PATRIMONIULUI CULTURAL
CENTRUL DE ARHEOLOGIE

REVISTA ARHEOLOGICĂ

Redactor șef/Editor-in-chief: dr. Ghenadie Sîrbu
Secretar de redacție/editorial secretary: Livia Sîrbu

Colegiul de redacție/Editorial Board

Dr. hab. **Igor Bruiako** (*Odesa*), dr. **Ludmila Bacumenco-Pîrnău** (*Chișinău*), dr. hab. **Dumitru Boghian** (*Târgu Frumos*), dr. **Roman Croitor** (*Aix-en-Provence*), dr. **Lilia Dergaciov** (*Chișinău*), dr. hab. **Valentin Dergaciov** (*Chișinău*), dr. **Alexandr Diachenko** (*Kiev*), dr. **Vasile Diaconu** (*Târgu Neamț*), dr. **Mariana Gugeanu** (*Iași*), prof. dr. hab. **Svend Hansen** (*Berlin*), prof. dr. hab. **Elke Kaiser** (*Berlin*), dr. **Maia Kașuba** (*Sankt Petersburg*), dr. **Sergiu Matveev** (*Chișinău*), prof. dr. hab. **Michael Meyer** (*Berlin*), dr. **Octavian Munteanu** (*Chișinău*), prof. dr. hab. **Sergiu Musteață** (*Chișinău/Târgoviște*), prof. dr. **Eugen Nicolae** (*București*), prof. dr. hab. **Gheorghe Postică** (*Chișinău*), dr. hab. **Eugen Sava** (*Chișinău*), dr. **Angela Simalcsik** (*Iași*), dr. hab. **Sergei Skoryi** (*Kiev*), prof. dr. **Victor Spinei**, membru al Academiei Române (*București, Iași*), prof. dr. **Marzena Szmyt** (*Poznan*), dr. **Nicolai Telnov** (*Chișinău*), dr. hab. **Petr Tolochko**, membru al Academiei Naționale de Științe a Ucrainei (*Kiev*), dr. **Denis Topal** (*Chișinău*), dr. **Vlad Vornic** (*Chișinău*), dr. **Aurel Zanoci** (*Chișinău*).

Manuscrisele, cărțile și revistele pentru schimb, precum și orice alte materiale se vor trimite pe adresa: Colegiul de redacție al „Revistei Arheologice”, Centrul de Arheologie, Institutul Patrimoniului Cultural, bd. Ștefan cel Mare și Sfânt 1, MD-2001, Chișinău, Republica Moldova

Рукописи, книги и журналы для обмена, а также другие материалы необходимо посылать по адресу: редакция «Археологического Журнала», Центр археологии, Институт культурного наследия, бул. Штефан чел Маре ши Сфынт 1, MD-2001 Кишинэу, Республика Молдова

Manuscripts, books and reviews for exchange, as well as other papers are to be sent to the editorship of the “Archaeological Magazine”, Archaeology Centre, Institute of Cultural Heritage, 1 Stefan cel Mare si Sfânt bd., MD-2001 Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

Toate lucrările publicate în revistă sunt recenzate de specialiști în domeniu după modelul *double blind peer-review*
Все опубликованные материалы рецензируются специалистами по модели *double blind peer-review*
All the papers to be published will be reviewed by experts according to the *double blind peer-review* model

© IPC, 2023

CUPRINS – СОДЕРЖАНИЕ – CONTENTS

STUDII – ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ – RESEARCHES

Hülya Çalışkan Akgül (<i>Trabzon</i>), Valery Manko (<i>Kyev</i>), Didem Turan (<i>Trabzon</i>), Guram Chkhatarashvili (<i>Batumi</i>), Sinan Kılıç (<i>Van</i>) New Epipalaeolithic sites in the southeastern Black Sea area and a question about the marine network of lunates with bipolar retouched arcs makers5
Pia Palaguta (<i>Sankt-Peterburg</i>) Cucuteni-Tripollye: ceramic assemblage, periodization, cultural development. Some general reflection30
Сергей Скорый (<i>Киeв</i>) Бронзовые скипетры скифской эпохи46
Николай Николаев (<i>Измаил</i>) Каноб, сын Трасидаманта, ольвиополит62

MATERIALE ŞI CERCETĂRI DE TEREN – МАТЕРИАЛЫ И ПОЛЕВЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ – PAPERS AND SURVEYS

Irina Rusu (<i>Suceava</i>) O aşezare de tip Chişinău-Corlăteni din Câmpia Prutului de Mijloc (contribuţii la conturarea peisajului arheologic al satului Romanovca, r-nul Ungheni)69
Vasyl Orlyk (<i>Kropyvnytsk</i>), Mark Pyzyk (<i>Vienna</i>) A hoard of Pontic coins from the time of Mithridates VI Eupator from the chora of Olbia87
Игорь Сапожников, Александр Синельников (<i>Одесса-Киeв</i>) Погребальные памятники второй-третьей четверти IV в. до н.э. у Аджидерской крепости на берегу Днестровского лимана100

DISCUȚII – ДИСКУССИИ – DISCUSSIONS

Игорь Сапожников (<i>Одесса-Киeв</i>) Курганы и населенные пункты Украины и Молдовы в 1830 году по материалам балканской экспедиции Г. Гуцы-Венелина118
--

CERCETĂRI INTERDISCIPLINARE – МЕЖДИСЦИПЛИНАРНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ – INTERDISCIPLINARY SURVEYS

Tetiana Goshko, Mikhail Videiko (<i>Kyev</i>) Research on early medieval weights: Materials and technologies138
Mariana Gugeanu (<i>Iaşi</i>) Restaurare-conservare textilă arheologică liturgică – Omoforul mare. Studiu de caz145
Mariana Gugeanu, Daniela Sălăjanţ, Maria Geba, Lăcrămioara Stratulat (<i>Iaşi</i>) Medalioane pictate şi galoane textile – componente ale mitrei mitropolitului Gavriil Bănulescu-Bodoni. Cercetare şi restaurare-conservare153

**RECENZII ȘI PREZENTĂRI DE CARTE –
РЕЦЕНЗИИ И КНИЖНОЕ ОБОЗРЕНИЕ – PAPER AND BOOK REVIEW**

V. Sîrbu, C. Schuster (eds.), <i>Necropolele preistorice de la Brăilița, în zona Dunării de Jos. O nouă abordare</i> , Editura Cetatea de Scaun, Editura Istros a Muzeului Brăilei „Carol I”, Târgoviște-Brăila, 2022, 591 p., ISBN 978-606-537-598-7/ISBN 978-606-654-493-1 (Vasile Diaconu, <i>Târgu-Neamț</i>)	161
Ion Ursu , <i>Populațiile turanice din spațiul est-carpatic în secolele X-XIV</i> , Editura Pontos, Chișinău, 2022, 390 p., ISBN 978-9975-72-697-9 (Ludmila Bacumenco-Pîrnău, <i>Chișinău/Iași</i>)	163
LISTA ABREVIERILOR – СПИСОК СОКРАЩЕНИЙ – LIST OF ABBREVIATION	166
INFORMAȚII ȘI CONDIȚIILE DE EDITARE A REVISTEI ARHEOLOGICE	167
ИНФОРМАЦИЯ И УСЛОВИЯ ИЗДАНИЯ АРХЕОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ЖУРНАЛА	168
INFORMATION AND CONDITION OF PUBLICATION IN THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL MAGAZINE	169

STUDII – ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ – RESEARCHES

Hülya Çalışkan Akgül, Valery Manko,
Didem Turan, Guram Chkhatarashvili, Sinan Kılıç

New Epipalaeolithic sites in the southeastern Black Sea area and a question about the marine network of lunates with bipolar retouched arcs makers

Key words: Final Pleistocene, Karain B Culture, Late Natufian culture, Taubodrakian culture, lunates with bipolar retouching, microburin technique, marine network.

Cuvinte cheie: Holocenul timpuriu, cultura Karain B, cultura Natufian târziu, cultura Taubodrak, lame și microlame cu spate, tehnica prin presare, zonă culturală maritimă.

Ключевые слова: финальный плейстоцен, культура Караин В, поздняя натуфийская культура, таубодракская культура, сегменты с биполярной ретушью, микрорезцовая техника, морская культурная область.

Hülya Çalışkan Akgül, Valery Manko, Didem Turan, Guram Chkhatarashvili, Sinan Kılıç

New Epipalaeolithic sites in the southeastern Black Sea area and a question about the marine network of lunates with bipolar retouched arcs makers

New finds at the sites of Koskarlı and Kaledere caves near Trabzon have shown a connection between these sites and finds of bipolar retouched lunates. Such lunates are known from the Near East (Late Natufian Culture), Antalya and Cappadocia (Karain B culture), the east coast of the Aegean Sea, Lemnos Island, the Sea of Marmara, and the Crimea. All known sites with lunates are associated with the Late Pleistocene. A study of the sites of Koskarlı and Kaledere has shown that the technology of bipolar retouched lunates production also spread to the southeastern Black Sea region. Finds from the Trabzon caves have led to a re-evaluation of several sites in western Georgia where lunates of this type have also been found. All the sites were located at a short distance from the seacoast. This circumstance suggests that in the second half of the XIII-XI millennium B.C. there was a maritime cultural and historical area that was the result of migratory activity. The center of the resettlement was the Antalya region. The migration of the carriers of this industry preceded the beginning of the neolithization process in the coastal areas of the four seas.

Hülya Çalışkan Akgül, Valery Manko, Didem Turan, Guram Chkhatarashvili, Sinan Kılıç

Noi situri epipaleolitice în zona sud-estică a Mării Negre și o întrebare despre rețeaua marină de luntre cu creatori de arcuri rețușate bipolare

Noile descoperiri din siturile din peșterile Koskarlı și Kaledere de lângă Trabzon au arătat o legătură între aceste situri și descoperirile de segmente bipolare rețușate. Astfel de segmente sunt cunoscute în Orientul Apropiat (cultura Natufian târziu), Antalia și Capadocia (cultura Karain B), coasta de est a Mării Egee, insula Lemnos, Marea Marmara și Crimeea. Toate siturile cunoscute cu segmente sunt asociate cu Pleistocenul târziu. Un studiu al siturilor de la Koskarlı și Kaledere a arătat că tehnologia de producere a segmentelor cu rețușuri bipolare s-a răspândit și în regiunea sud-estică a Mării Negre. Descoperirile din peșterile de la Trabzon au dus la reevaluarea mai multor situri din vestul Georgiei, unde au fost descoperite, de asemenea, segmente de acest tip. Toate siturile erau situate la o distanță scurtă de coasta maritimă. Această împrejurare sugerează că în a doua jumătate a mileniului XIII-XI î.Chr. a existat o zonă culturală și istorică maritimă care a fost rezultatul unei activități migratorii. Centrul relocării a fost regiunea Antalia. Migrația purtătorilor acestei industrii a precedat începutul procesului de neolitizare în zonele de coastă ale celor patru mări.

Хулия Чалишкан Акгуль, Валерий Манько, Дидем Туран, Гурам Чхатарашвили, Синан Килич

Новые эpipaleолитические стоянки в Восточном Причерноморье и вопрос о морской культурно-исторической области носителей технологии изготовления сегментов с биполярной ретушью

Новые находки на стоянках в пещерах Коскарли и Каледере у Трапзонда показали связь этих стоянок с находками сегментов с биполярной ретушью. Такие сегменты были известны на территории Ближнего Востока (поздняя натуфийская культура), на памятниках Анталии и Каппадокии (культура Караин В), в Эгее, на острове Лемнос, на Мраморном море, в Крыму. Все известные стоянки с сегментами связаны с концом плейстоцена. Исследование стоянок Коскарли и Каледере показало, что технология изготовления сегментов с биполярной ретушью распространялась и в Восточном Причерноморье. Находки в пещерах у Трапзонда позволили по-новому оценить материалы ряда многих стоянок на западе Грузии, где также отмечено наличие сегментов указанного типа. Все стоянки находились в небольшом отдалении от

берегов моря. Данное обстоятельство позволяет предположить, что во второй половине XIII–XI тыс. до н.э. существовала морская культурно историческая область, которая образовалась в результате миграционной активности. Центром расселения был регион Анталии. Миграция носителей индустрии с сегментами с биполярной ретушью предшествовала началу процесса неолитизации прибрежных районов четырех морей.

Introduction

In 2019–22, the Koskarlı and Kaledere caves were found in the coastal areas of the Black Sea near Trabzon. A collection of flint and obsidian artefacts was found on the surface and in natural sections. The study of the collections showed that the camp complexes have analogues in Turkey as well as in Greece, Ukraine, and Georgia. The main characteristic unites the sites located in the regions connected to the Mediterranean, Aegean, Marmara, and Black Seas. These are the presence in complexes of lunates with bipolar retouched arcs. These geometric microliths were produced using a microburin technique associated with the production of short, curved blades and bladelets using a hard hammer. The identification of several remote sites with common stone industry features has raised the question of why such industries spread across the basins of the four seas. This process can be explained by the convergent development of lithic industries in peripheral regions, the existence of a system of cultural contacts between the inhabitants of peripheral regions, and the migration of populations from a region, which led to the settlement of carriers of the tradition of making lunates with bipolar retouching. Several dozen sites with such lunates are currently known. These are the sites of the Natufian, Karain B, Taubodrakian and Imeretian cultures (fig. 1). A study of the interaction between these cultures is the subject of our research.

Methods

The main task of our research is to show the character of the relationships between the bearers of different Epipalaeolithic cultures.

We have suggested 3 possible reasons for the similarity of these cultures. A convergent development of several cultures is possible, but the evidence for convergence must be as follows.

1. The impossibility of carriers of one culture entering a region where we observe a similar culture.
2. Evidence of two or more industries at different times.

3. The existence of evidence for the origin of the industries being compared on a local basis.

If we can demonstrate the presence of at least one of these three criteria, we can say that convergent development has taken place.

Cultural contacts between distant populations are difficult to prove. The necessary conditions for proof would be such features of the industries being compared as

1. There is no complete similarity between the industries. The similarity consists only in the presence of similar stone tools, including geometric microliths.
2. There is evidence of synchronization in the development of the various industries.
3. Possibility of contacts between the bearers of two or more stone industries.

The proof of cultural contacts between the bearers of two or more industries can only be the presence of all three criteria. It should be noted that even the presence of all the criteria does not allow us to speak of an exceptional possibility of cultural contact, since the diffusion of small groups would be related to the same criteria.

The criteria of migration in archaeology have been identified by L.S. Klein [Klein 1999]. They are:

1. Complex similarity (agreement on the main typological characteristics).
2. Spontaneity, abrupt change of cultures at the end point of the migration.
3. The possibility of joining the migratory activity in time and space.

L.S. Klein felt that all three criteria were redundant. We share that view. We may not always be able to fully characterize a particular industry, we may not have absolute chronological data. Nevertheless, the existence of at least two criteria already allows us to talk about the possibility of migration.

The existence of three options for solving the problem of the similarity of cultures does not exclude the possibility of 2 or 3 factors acting simultaneously.

The solution of the main problem is linked to the solution of several related problems.

Fig. 1. The map of sites with lunates with bipolar retouch. 1 – Saffulim; 2 – Beidha; 3 – TBAS 102; 4 – Rosh Horesha; 5 – Rosh Zin; 6 – Jeriho; 7 – Raqefet; 8 – Nahal Ein Gev II; 9 – Hayonim Terrace; 10 – Baaz; 11 – Abu Hureyra I; 12 – Dederiyeh Cave; 13 – Eşek Deresi Cave; 14 – Direkli Cave; 15 – Beldibi; 16 – Belbaşı; 17 – Hurma; 18 – Karain B, Kızılin cave; 19 – Öküzi; 20 – Pınarbaşı; 21 – Kocaman; 22 – Ouriakos, Agia Marina, Peristereonas; 23 – Gümüşdere; 24 – Ağaçlı; 25 – Domali; 26 – Kaledere; 27 – Koskarlı; 28 – Gurianta, Anaseuli II; 29 – Sakazhiya; 30 – Dzudzuana; 31 – Satsurbliia; 32 – Paluri; 33 – Fatma-Koba; 34 – Shan-Koba; 35 – Vodopadny Grotto; 36 – Skelyastiy Grotto; 37 – Bilolissya.

1. To prove the existence of different industries with bipolar retouching at the same time or at different times. The solution to this problem involves the use of radiocarbon chronology and stratigraphic observations.

2. Mapping of lunates with bipolar retouching in search of possible migration routes.

3. Typological analysis of complexes of lunates with bipolar retouching to determine their total or partial similarity. A. Marks typology will be used for this purpose. Marks typology will be used for this purpose [Marks 1976].

Geographic position of the Research Area

The prehistoric cultures in the Trabzon area are poorly understood due to the lack of insuffi-

cient archaeological data [Çalışkan 2016]. Concentrated archaeological research in this area is scarce, and existing research mostly focuses on the so called “Greek colonies” and Roman and Medieval periods. The coastline of the region was sparsely populated until Aegean merchants arrived according to the available archaeological data. Therefore, the Trabzon Survey Project (TYAP), started in 2018, primarily focused on the preclassical periods in the region. Nevertheless, the findings from Koskarlı cave in Düzköy district and from Kaledere-West cave in Tonya district, Trabzon province, where flint and obsidian chipped stone tools were found in 2019-2021, change both the expectations of the survey project and the status of the prehistory of the southeastern

coast of the Black Sea region from what was once known as “terra incognita” to a region whose early prehistory is albeit partly much better understood than before [Çalışkan, Dinçer 2021].

The southeastern part of the Black Sea Basin, in which also the Trabzon province is located, constitutes a transition area between Anatolia and Caucasus. This location makes the Trabzon area unique in terms of regional transit routes for pre-historic time periods as for today.

Research area includes the southern part of Kale valley in Düzköy district and the Kaledere Stream Valley in Tonya district in the province of Trabzon, both of the rivers flow into the Black Sea. Cave formations draw attention on both sides of the rocky valleys, which are quite steep slope in most places.

The region consists of geological units ranging from Paleozoic to Quaternary. These units generally rejuvenate towards the north and northeast [Güven 1998]. The Paleozoic terrain in the southeast is the main structure and consists of gneisses, mica schists and schists. After this, the youngest terrain consists of Jurassic and Upper Jurassic-Lower Cretaceous aged units. These units are composed of volcanic rocks and limestones with various characteristics and also contain flints in some places [Gattinger

et al. 1962, 11]. The Cretaceous rocks are generally composed of volcanic units formed under the sea. Basalt and dacite columns within the volcanic units are quite common in the area. Upper Cretaceous units include sandstones, marl, shale, clay, limestone and tuffs [Gattinger et al. 1962, 13-15]. Jurassic and Cretaceous aged units lie to the south of the Düzköy region, and are faulted in some places. The rocks have been altered due to moisture and precipitation, so chemical dissolution is very intense. The most recent geological formations are in the form of well-formed pebble and clay layers showing a steep coastal type generally fill a narrow coastline or close to the rivers, and observed only up to 50-100 m above sea level [Gattinger et al. 1962, 18-19].

Sites in the Province of Trabzon

Koskarlı cave, situated 1.5 km west of Çayırbağı village in Düzköy district, at an elevation of 20 m above Söğütlü (Galanima) Creek, is located at an elevation of 1020 m above the sea level and faces south-east (in the northwest-southeast direction). The cave was developed in a pyroclastic layer, also sedimentary blocks and pebbles are represented in this layer (fig. 2). The cave is 26 m in depth and 19 m in width. The height of the cave entrance is 7,5 m, reduces to 3,5 m at the end (fig. 3). Flint and obsidian artifacts

Fig. 2. Koskarlı Cave from South.

Fig. 3. Plan and the A-A' section of the Koskarlı Cave.

are scattered on the floor, both at the entrance and inside the cave. The cave is of great archaeological importance since it represents the first example of Pre-Neolithic lithic artifacts in Pontides.

An area about 4 m northeast of the cave entrance, probably already eroded and naturally damaged by the stream, was discovered in 2021. This cut, located about 20 m above the bottom of the creek, is about 2.5 m in height and 3 m in width (fig. 4). Also, in this section numerous flint and obsidian stone tools were found.

In the next valley, about 4 km westward from the Koskarlı cave, Kaledere caves are located in the southwest of Tonya district, Trabzon province, on the northern slope of the Kaledere valley, which is an arm of the Fol stream (fig. 1). The site about 1000 m above the sea level is composed of volcanic rocks, and divided into two parts by a vertical fault crack. In the east there is a large cave called

the Kaledere-East, developed on the stratification plane between the volcanic rocky strata, and the Kaledere-West is a great rock shelter (fig. 5). As far as can be seen, in front of both there is a terrestrial deposit covered an area of 120×30 m and has a thickness of about 15 m. This deposit seems to be formed by the crumbling of the cliff surface and cave ceiling due to chemical dissolution, and accumulated in front.

Three small rock cavities (A, B and C) open to the large terrace of the Kaledere-West, which is about 60 m above the valley bottom (fig. 6). Some large rock blocks that seem to have fallen off the cliff are standing on the terrace surface covered with gravel and sheep dung, as the floor of rock cavities. In the biggest chamber (Chamber A) in the west, flint and obsidian fragments were found in clusters on the left side of the entrance. Similar pieces were also recovered in front of the Chamber B. Chamber C to the east is a larger rock cavity located under the fault crack. No archaeological remains were encountered in the Chamber C.

To the west of the terrace some lithic material is found in a rather high section formed during the gravel intake (fig. 5). The layers of the section are observed in this cut and go to the east along the slope of the terrace in front of the rock shelter. The discovery of flint and obsidian chipped stone tools in this approximately 11 m high section indicates the importance of the side for understanding the stratigraphy of early human activities in the region.

Stratigraphy

The Koskarlı cave [Çalışkan, Dinçer 2021] has preserved an area of about 20 square meters near the cave wall, where a natural cut has been made by the debris. Examination of the cut revealed the following picture:

Layer 1. A layer of modern humus is preserved in some areas, 0 to 5 cm thick.

Layer 2. The layer of ancient soil can be traced to a depth of 0.5-0.7 m. The layer is light brown and contains admixtures of fine gravel.

Layer 3. Layer of pale-yellow loess, traced to the depth of 1.0-1.2 m.

Layer 2 contains interlayers of tile-like detritus. There are at least 8 such interlayers. These interlayers were formed by the destruction of the cave ceiling.

Fig. 4. A drone picture of Koskarlı cliff and the natural cut made by the debris in the north.

Fig. 5. Kaledere rock cliff with the cave, rock shelter and the section formed during the gravel intake.

The presence of these interlayers created perfect conditions for the saving of homogeneous stone complexes, which were left at short intervals. In layer 2 there is evidence of fire pits. The presence of charcoal, bone charcoal and faunal remains is also associated with layer 2. Layer 3 is represented by a rather homogeneous sediment. No lithic artefacts were found.

The character of the section allows it to be interpreted as Late Pleistocene and Early Holocene. Similar sections have been repeatedly investigated in the coastal areas of the Black Sea in Ukraine.

H.P. Gerasimenko associates [Гepaсимeнкo 1997] the loess similar to Layer 3 with Early Dryas (15-14.5-12.8 BP uncal), and soils similar to Layer 2 with the stadia of Bølling (12.8-12.2 BP uncal)

and Allerød (11.8-11.1 BP uncal). It is possible that deposition of Layer 2 may have continued into the Early Holocene to the Atlantic.

Kaledere cave had no natural cuts, but inspection of the ruined areas confirmed the similarity of the stratigraphy of Koskarlı cave. Collection of finds in the ruined areas allowed us to find out that the cultural layer is located at a depth of up to 1 m under a layer of massive blocks of the cave ceiling collapse.

Thus, the traced stratigraphy and the nature of the stone complex allow us to date both cave sites to the Final Pleistocene (12.8-10.3 BP uncal).

Stone complexes

The complexes at both sites show the use of a variety of raw materials. This diversity is probably due to the poverty of the raw material base and the need to make maximum use of local resources. Red, green, and yellow flint predominate. The sources of the raw materials are not known. The origin of the rare obsidian finds is also unknown.

The cave complex of Koskarlı cave contains 5 cores. The typology of the cores is determined by the poverty of the raw material base. Even low-quality flint was used to make short blades and bladelets. A multiplatform core has 4 fronts for blades removal (fig. 7,1). The negatives of the blades are no more than 6 cm long. Another multiplatform core was used until it was no longer possible to obtain blades (fig. 7,2). There is a single platform monofrontal core which was discontinued after attempting platform corrections. There are 3 two-platform cores. Two are monofrontal (fig 7,4-5) and one is prismatic (fig. 7,6). All cores were knapped using the direct percussion method with a soft hammer.

All blades (42 items) are curved in profile, up to 6 cm long and 1.2-2 cm wide. Only 5 bladelets are found in the complex; they are represented by medial segments and have a width of 1.0-1.2 cm. Flakes (79 items) are up to 5 cm wide, primary flakes are very rare.

Fig. 6. Kaledere-West plan with the sections of A-A' and B-B', the Rock Shelter.

There are 36 tools in complex. Fourteen of these are scrapers. Four types of scrapers were indicated. There are 2 end-scrapers on blades (fig. 8,3-4). Other types of scrapers are linked with flakes blanks. There are 3 end-scrapers on massive flakes (fig. 8,1,10,14), 6 side-scrapers on flakes (fig. 8,5-6,8,11-13), and 2 carinated scrapers (fig. 8,2,9).

There are only 2 burins in complex. One of them is burin on truncated faceted massive blade (fig. 9,1), other – angle-burin on massive flake (fig. 9,2).

There is 1 composite tool: burin on truncated faceted blade – end-scrapers (fig. 9,3).

Five blades with semi-steep retouch are present in complex (fig. 9,4-8). There are 5 notched blades. Two blades have small notches on edges (fig. 9,12-13). Three blades have long notches (2-3 cm), which are linked with semi-steep retouching (fig. 9,9-11). Two of them are combined with end-scrapers (fig. 9,10-11). It is possible that these tools were originally scrapers. Subsequently, a reduction strategy led to the re-designation of scrapers as notched blades.

There are 4 perforators in complex. One of them is a drill on massive flake with alternating retouched distal end (fig. 10,1). There is a bladelet with alternated retouched edges (fig. 10,10). Other perforators are piercing tools on blades (fig. 10,2-3). There are 4 retouched flakes (fig. 10,4-7).

Lunates are the most valuable finds at the site. One of them is symmetric lunate on blade with bipolar retouched arc (fig. 10,8). The retouched arc removed the fringe on the blank of lunate. This lunate's type titled "lemon slice" in Ukrainian literature [Sapozhnikov, Sapozhnikova 2011, 88]. Other lunate with bipolar retouched arc is symmetric too but have saving fringes (fig. 10,9). This lunate has macrofractures traces on long edge and on the point of contact of arc with edge. Note that this lunate has a slight asymmetry due to the protruding corner of the arch. This circumstance indicates the use of the microburin technique.

There is one tool in a complex that could be unfinished lunates, a mistake of the craftsman. This tool has a notched edge, prepared for microburin removal (fig. 10,11).

The Kaledere complex is an absolute analogue of the Koskarlı complex. We observe here the same flint and obsidian knapping technique, we note the use of the same raw materials.

There are 4 cores in complex. One of them – single-platform prismatic core with dihedral platform (fig. 11,1). Only one two-platform core was found. It's a monofrontal core with changed direct of percussion (fig. 11,2). The appearance of this type of cores are linked with reduction strategy, when second platform formed after inability to use the first platform. The strategy of cores reduction led to appearance of multiplatform cores (fig. 11,3). One of kinds of single-platform cores is the core with narrow surface (fig. 11,4).

Fig. 7. Koskarlı cave. Cores.

The big number of blades (17 items) are curved in profile, up to 6 cm long and 1.2-2 cm wide. There are two blades with straight profile. There are 5 bladelets in the complex; but one bladelet was a blank for microlith. Flakes (74 items) are up to 5 cm wide, primary flakes are very rare.

There are 11 scrapers in complex. One of them is double end-scrapers on flake (fig. 12,1). Two side-scrapers on flakes represent rare type “with noses” (fig. 12,2,4). Three side-scrapers were made on blades blanks (fig. 12,3,5-6). Four end-scrapers were made on flakes with convergent (fig. 12,8), divergent (fig. 12,7; fig. 13,2) and parallel edges (fig. 13,4). Only one end-scrapers was made on blade with notches (fig. 13,3).

Only one burin was found in complex. It's angle burin on blade (fig. 13,5). Three retouched blades are present in complex (fig. 13,6-7,9). Fine dorsal and semi-steep ventral retouching was used. There are 3 notched blades in complex (fig. 13,8,10-11).

Only 3 microliths were found in Kaledere. One of them is chipped lunate with bipolar retouching on arc (fig. 12,9). There is an asymmetric triangle with bipolar retouched sides (fig. 12,11). There is 1 non-geometric microlith. It's a proximal segment of backed bladelet (fig. 12,10).

Kaledere cave complex contain a possibly mixt of Middle Palaeolithic tools. Possibly, Levallois point was find. This tool has faceted platform

Fig. 8. Koskarlı cave. Scrapers.

and ventral semi-steep retouch on sides (fig. 14,1). Other tool is possibly Mousterian point on convergent blade (fig. 14,2). Levallois core was found too (fig. 13,1). These findings can be linked with possible Middle Palaeolithic layer under the Epipalaeolithic Layer.

Thus, the complexes of both sites show typological unity and are associated with the manufacture of lunates with bipolar retouch.

Discussion

Analogies of the Trabzon sites in the eastern Black Sea region.

The finds of lunates with bipolar retouching in the Trabzon area are not unique in the eastern

Black Sea region. Homogeneous complexes are not known but finds of lunates of this type are present as mechanical admixtures at several sites in western Georgia.

A series of 13 lunates of this type is present in the Anaseuli II complex [Nebieridze 1972, fig. 10]. The site of Anaseuli II is associated with the Odishi Neolithic culture. However, similar finds are not associated with any of the other sites of this Neolithic culture. This fact leads us to believe that the Final Pleistocene cultural layer was not observed during the excavations. All lunates have a symmetrical shape, some of the lunates have removed fringes on the blade blanks.

A series of 5 lunates with bipolar retouching were found at the multilayer site of Gurianta

Fig. 9. 1-2. Burins. 3. Scraper-burin. 4-7. Retouched blades. 8-11. Notched blades.

[Nebieridze 1972, fig. 37]. Three of these lunates have fringes removed. Unfortunately, the low level of research on the site does not allow the lunates to be correlated with other materials.

Four lunates with bipolar retouching were found on site Paluri [Grigolia 1977, fig. 11]. Unfortunately, the author of the excavations was unable to separate the Epipaleolithic and Neolithic layers.

Two complexes with lunates with bipolar retouching are radiocarbon dated. These are the complex of layer B [Golovanova, Doronichev

2012, fig. 15] from the Dzudzuana site (Table 1, 1) and the complex of layer 4 [Golovanova, Doronichev 2012, fig. 13] from the Sakazhiya site (Table 1, 2). Both are associated with the Allerød interstadial. Unfortunately, in both complexes the lunates are a mechanical admixture to the Epigravettian materials.

Are there any sites in the South Caucasus with segments like those at Trabzon? We think that the proximity of the regions and their short distance from the Black Sea coast suggest the develop-

Fig. 10. Koskarlı cave. 1-3, 10. Perforators. 4-7. Retouched flakes. 8-9. Lunates. 11. Lunates chip.

ment of a single archaeological culture in the eastern Black Sea area. The lunates from Dzudzuana and Sakazhiya are not numerous and were admixtures to the main complexes. The lunates found at the other sites are in series, which can be an indicator of the presence of the technology bearers at the sites. The appearance of lunates in Dzudzuana and Sakazhiya could be the result of contacts between their inhabitants and the people who left the sites of Anaseuli II, Guriant and Paluri.

The radiocarbon dates of Dzudzuana and Sakazhiya are fully consistent with the assumed dating of Koskarlı cave, and do not contradict the data on the stratigraphy of the Trabzon sites. This circumstance gives us one more reason to consider Turkish and Georgian complexes as belonging to the same culture. Naturally, only further parallel investigations of the sites in eastern Turkey and western Georgia will make it possible to finally resolve the problem.

First appearance of complexes with lunates with bipolar retouched arcs

As we have already written, the sites of lunates with bipolar retouching were distributed over a large area. Accordingly, we must determine the primary center of diffusion of the technology of making these geometric microlites. The only way to determine the place where the technology appeared is by analyzing radiocarbon dates. Such analysis leads us to the area of Antalya (south-western Turkey).

The earliest dates associated with the complexes of these lunates were obtained from the Karain B and Öküzini sites (Table 1, 3-11). The complexes of these sites are associated with the Karain B culture [Albrecht 1988]. All Karain B sites are linked with lunates, trapezes, and triangles with bipolar retouching (fig. 15,1-6).

The Karain B culture begins to develop in the period before the Bølling warming. The early

Table 1. Radiocarbon dates.

№	BP (uncal)	Lab. №	Material	Site	BC (cal) 95,4% prob.	Culture	References
1	11700±80	OxA-7853	Bone	Sakaghiya, Layer 4	11816- 11459	Imeretian	Nioradze, Otte 2000
2	11500±75	RTT-3282	Bone	Dzudzuana, Layer B	11553- 11236	Imeretian	Bar-Yosef et al. 2011
3	11250±200	Hd- 10028/10227	Bone	Karain B	11537- 10816	Karain B	Erdoğu et al. 2003
4	11800±330	Hd-10027	Bone	Karain B	12927- 11145	Karain B	Erdoğu et al. 2003
5	12280±275	Hd- 10030/10229	Bone	Karain B	13314- 11656	Karain B	Erdoğu et al. 2003
6	12500±75	HD- 13351/12985	Charcoal	Öküzini, Layer VIA	13133- 12362	Karain B	Bayon et al. 2002
7	12585±280	GX-16284	Charcoal	Öküzini, Layer VIA	13816- 11936	Karain B	Bayon et al. 2002
8	12610±180	HD- 13352/13343	Charcoal	Öküzini, Layer VIA	13571- 12235	Karain B	Bayon et al. 2002
9	10440±115	RT-1441	Charcoal	Öküzini, Layer Ia2	10737- 9990	Karain B	Bayon et al. 2002
10	11440±100	Lv-1895	Charcoal	Öküzini, Layer Ia2	11546- 11173	Karain B	Bayon et al. 2002
11	11730±90	ETH-8032	Charcoal	Öküzini, Layer Ia2	11842- 11481	Karain B	Bayon et al. 2002
12	12945±255	OxA 16536	Bone	Pınarbaşı	14353- 12526	Karain B	Baird et al. 2013
13	12580±55	OxA 16535	Bone	Pınarbaşı	13223- 12597	Karain B	Baird et al. 2013
14	11445±40	BA130239	Bone	Pınarbaşı	11488- 11238	Karain B	Baird et al. 2013
15	11400±45	BA130242	Bone	Pınarbaşı	11446- 11220	Karain B	Baird et al. 2013
16	11190±45	BA130241	Bone	Pınarbaşı	11231- 11053	Karain B	Baird et al. 2013
17	10910±520	AA-1462	Charcoal	Beidha	12066- 9319	Late Natufian	Byrd 1988
18	9600±200	OxA-476	Bone	Abu Hureyra I	9655- 8346	Late Natufian	Housley 1994
19	11450±300	OxA-883	Seeds	Abu Hureyra I	12066- 10815	Late Natufian	Housley 1994
20	10470±121	KIA-11576	Charcoal	Baaz	10757- 10000	Late Natufian	Conrad 2002
21	10667±97	KIA-11578	Charcoal	Baaz	10875- 10522	Late Natufian	Conrad 2002
22	10942±65	KIA-11577	Charcoal	Baaz	11112- 10801	Late Natufian	Conrad 2002
23	10800±180	GL-70	Charcoal	Jericho	11211- 10229	Late Natufian	Weinstein 1984

24	11086±90	BM-1407	Charcoal	Jericho	11215-10836	Late Natufian	Weinstein 1984
25	11166±107	P-376	Charcoal	Jericho	11347-10887	Late Natufian	Weinstein 1984
26	10580±140	I-7030	Bone	Rakefet	10811-10049	Late Natufian	Gorring-Morris 1987
27	10980±260	I-7032	Bone	Rakefet	11533-10247	Late Natufian	Gorring-Morris 1987
28	10490±430	SMU-90	Bone	Rosh Horesha	11356-9201	Late Natufian	Larson, Marks 1977
29	10490±430	SMU-9	Bone	Rosh Horesha	11356-9201	Late Natufian	Larson, Marks 1977
30	10880±280	SMU-10	Bone	Rosh Horesha	11406-10047	Late Natufian	Larson, Marks 1977
31	10930±130	OxA-2136	Charcoal	Saflulim	11151-10766	Late Natufian	Housley 1994
32	11150±100	OxA-2869	Charcoal	Saflulim	11293-10883	Late Natufian	Housley 1994
33	10460±45	RTD-7449	Charcoal	Nahal Ein Gev II	10671-10153	Late Natufian	Grosman et al. 2016
34	10445±45	RTD-7451	Charcoal	Nahal Ein Gev II	10666-10150	Late Natufian	Grosman et al. 2016
35	10340±40	RTD-7450	Charcoal	Nahal Ein Gev II	10517-9997	Late Natufian	Grosman et al. 2016
36	11040± 60	Beta-229411	Charcoal	TBAS 102	11146-10881	Late Natufian	Neeley 2010
37	11170±70	Beta-221179	Charcoal	TBAS 102	11282-10954	Late Natufian	Neeley 2010
38	11392±62	TERRA-102306b24	Charcoal	Dederiyeh Cave	11468-11212	Late Natufian	Nishiaki 2017
39	10935±62	TERRA-120804a14	Charcoal	Dederiyeh Cave	11109-10798	Late Natufian	Nishiaki 2017
40	11460±110	OxA-2572	Bone	Hayonim Terrace*	11626-11173	Late Natufian	Stutz 2004
41	11220±110	OxA-2569	Bone	Hayonim Terrace*	11374-10898	Late Natufian	Stutz 2004
42	10,390±45	GrA-53229	Bone	Ouriakos	10629-10052	Karain B	Efstratiou 2014
43	11620±110	OxA-5164	Bone	Skelyasty, Layer III-2	11806-11308	Taubodrakian	Cohen et al. 1996
44	11200±120	Ki-13153	Bone	Skelyasty, Layer III-3-A	11362-10894	Taubodrakian	Kovalchuk et al. 2021
45	12148±61	KIA-9568	Bone	Shan-Koba, Layer 6-2	12247-11856	Taubodrakian /Shankobian	Benecke 2006
46	11260±190	Ki-11086	Bone	Shan-Koba, Layer 6-1	11541-10821	Taubodrakian /Shankobian	Man'ko 2013
47	11645±59	KIA-9566	Bone	Shan-Koba, Layer 6-4	11655-11402	Taubodrakian /Shankobian	Benecke 2006
48	11299±53	KIA-9569	Bone	Shan-Koba, Layer 6-1	11351-11155	Taubodrakian /Shankobian	Benecke 2006

49	11170±45	GrA-50246	Bone	Shan-Koba, Layer 6	11223- 10985	Taubodrakian /Shankobian	Biagi et al. 2014
50	10871±58	KIA-9567	Bone	Shan-Koba, Layer 6-3	10951- 10781	Taubodrakian /Shankobian	Benecke 2006
51	9910±180	Ki-11085	Bone	Shan-Koba, Layer 6-1	10092- 8809	Taubodrakian /Shankobian	Манько 2013
52	9575±45	GrA-50244	Bone	Shan-Koba, Layer 4-4	9193- 8776	Taubodrakian /Shpankobian	Benece 2006
53	11415±50	OxA-34632	Bone	Satsurblia	11461- 11225	Epigravettian	Jones et al. 2015

* Without extremum dates

phases of the development of the Karain B culture are characterised by the complexes of layers VIII and VII of Öküzini. The materials from the Kızılın cave may be related to the same period [Kartal 2017]. The complexes of microliths in these layers can be called “proto-geometric”. Microliths are

represented by double-backed points and backed pieces with ventral retouched ends. A new stage of cultural development is associated with the Bølling Interstadial, when geometric microliths and the microburin technique appeared [Kozłowski, Kaczanowska 2004].

Fig. 11. Kaledere-West. 1-4. Cores.

Karain B is the eponymous site (Table 1, 3-5). The Epipalaeolithic complex reflects the transitional stage of cultural development when non-geometric and geometric microliths were produced simultaneously [Albrecht 1988]. An important observation is the use of bipolar retouching for both non-geometric and geometric microliths. Studies in recent years have shown that complexes with lunates with bipolar retouching are associated with the finding of single- and double-platform monofrontal cores, end scrapers and perforators [Yaçınkaya et al. 2014]. The presence of Karene-type scrapers is very important [Taşkıran et al. 2017].

Some researchers think that lunates with bipolar retouching were made in the Late Neolithic Karain B [Kartal 2018]. We do not support this view. In this case there is a mechanical mixing of different complexes.

Overall, a comparison of the Epipalaeolithic complexes at Trabzon and Karain B shows that the differences between them are minimal. Only the absence of non-geometric microliths in the Trabzon complexes is significant. However, this difference can be explained by chronological factors.

The subject of our study relates to layers VI-I – Ia2 of the Öküzini cave site (fig. 15,7-16). The appearance of lunates with bipolar retouching is associated with the Bølling Interstadial (Table 1, 6-25). Later complexes of lunates

Fig. 12. Kaledere-West. 1-8. Scrapers. 9-11. Microliths.

with bipolar retouching are dated to the end of the Pleistocene (Table 1, 9-11). The presence of lunates with bipolar and non-bipolar retouching is a characteristic of the Öküzini complexes [Kartal 2003; Leonard, Bayon 2006]. This circumstance is the result of a mechanical mixing of the complexes of the bearers of two different industries. This view is based on the fact that different complexes with two different types of lunates are known from the Anatolian region.

These are the Beldibi and Belbaşı complexes in Antalya. The lunates, trapezes and trian-

gles were made using the microburin technique [Bostancı 1959; 1962].

The sites described above probably represent the core area of the Karain B culture. The peculiarity of these sites is that they are located close to the sea. At the same time, sites of the Karain B culture are known beyond Antalya.

Sites of the Karain B culture beyond Antalya. East Mediterranean zone

Eşek Deresi cave located in Eşek Deresi Val-

Fig. 13. Kaledere-West. 1. Levallois core. 2-4. Scrapers. 5. Burin. 6-7, 9. Retouched blades. 8, 10-11. Notched blades.

ley in Cilicia. There are a series of lunates with bipolar retouching in the complex. Epipalaeolithic layer have radiocarbon date, but only calibrated result was published (10771-10631 cal BC) [Altınbilek-Algül et al. 2021].

Direkli Cave is the most informative site of the Karain B culture in East Mediterranean zone. The site is located in the Kahramanmaraş province of Turkey and was investigated using modern methods in 2007-2008 [Erek 2010].

Single platform monofrontal cores dominated in Direkli cave complex. There are end- and side-scrapers, perforators (drills and piercing

tolls), angle burins. There are big number of lunates with bipolar retouching (fig. 15,26-31). Trapezes and triangles with bipolar retouching sides are rare. The author of the study describes “backed curved bladelets” separately. We believe that this category of bladelets is no different from lunates with bipolar retouching. The shape of many backed curved bladelets is associated with macrofracture damage.

Direkli Cave is similar to the Belbaşı and Belbasi complexes in Antalya. The complex of Direkli Cave is homogeneous, without any previous additions. The appearance of these complexes marks

the beginning of the advance of the Epipalaeolithic population of Antalya to the east and northeast. The Direkli cave complex has not been dated, but we argue that it cannot be related to the geometric microlithic emergence phase of the Bølling Interstadial. The full absence of double-backed points and backed pieces with ventral retouched ends is main proof of more later age of site. It is more likely that the start of the eastward movement is related to the cooling that occurred not early then Dryas II.

Pınarbaşı is a multilayer site on Anatolian Plato [Baird 2012], which have evidence of Epipalaeolithic occupation during Bølling – Allerød (Table 1, 12-16). The site is associated with seasonal visits over a long period of time.

D. Baird is certain that the obsidian and flint artefacts were brought to the site in a finished form. The characteristics of obsidian and flint knapping are therefore not traceable. The main feature of the site is a series of 36 large lunates with “direct, inverse and bipolar backing” [Baird 2012, 186] and oval and round scrapers.

Pınarbaşı studies have shown that there is an undeniable connection between the occupants of the site and the Epipalaeolithic of Antalya. The similarities with Beldibi and Belbaşı are underlined. At the same time, similarities with Natufian and Late Natufian are discussed. This similarity is linked to the similar lunates with bipolar retouching making technique, with common features in the economy, in the similarity of the funerary practices [Baird et al. 2013].

We do not exclude the possibility of contacts between Early Natufian and Karain B cultures, but the intensification of contacts could only occur with Late Natufian habitation (Table 1, 17-41). The

earliest radiocarbon dates of Early Natufian (Table 1, 37-38) are synchronous with late Pınarbaşı dates. It is very likely that a change in lunates making technology by the Late Natufian bearers was under the influence of Eastern Mediterranean Karain B culture. The nature of this impact can be studied by analyzing the materials of the Late Natufian sites.

Early and Late Natufian are not distinct cultures. Stone knapping methods did not change. Single-platform cores dominated, with the use of opposed-platform and altered-orientation cores. The production of lunates and triangles was associated with the use of microburins. Backed blades are present in Natufian complexes, end scrapers dominate, burins are very rare. Backed knives, perforators, notched and denticulated blades are also present in Natufian complexes. A large number of lunates from early Natufian complexes were associated with Helwan retouching. The developmental trend of the Late Natufian led to the complete absence of Helwan lunates [Goring-Morris 1987].

The Dederiyeh cave complex in northwestern Syria, one of the northernmost Natufian sites, characterises the Late Natufian transitional phase (Nishiaki et al. 2017). Materials from the site include both Helwan-retouched lunates and bipolar-retouched lunates (fig. 15,32-39). The special feature of bipolar-retouched lunates is their long length (up to 4 cm). This feature points to parallels with Pınarbaşı and Direkli caves.

Only one other Late Natufian site is associated with long lunates. This is TBAS 102 in Jordan [Neeley 2010]. Notably, Dederiyeh Cave and TBAS 102 are the oldest Late Natufian sites.

Thus, the spread of bipolar retouched lunates could be the result of the penetration of small

Fig. 14. Kaledere-West. 1. Levallois point (?). 2. Mousterian point (?).

Fig. 15. Microliths (1-23, 26-54) and microburins (24-25). 1-6. Karain B [Albrecht 1988]. 7-16. Öküzini, Layer VIA [Leotard, Bayon 2006]. 17-25. Öküzini, Layer Ia2 [Leotard, Bayon 2006]. 26-31. Direkli cave [Erek 2010]. 32-39. Rosh Zin [Henry 1973]. 40-41. Kocaman [Cilingiroglu et al. 2020]. 42-45. Hurma [Atakuman et al. 2022]. 46-54. Ouriakos [Efstratiou et al. 2014].

groups of carriers of the Karain B culture into the Natufian area. It is also possible that there was no small group penetration and that the appearance of lunates with bipolar retouching was the result of cultural contacts between the bearers of the two cultures during the exchange of obsidian from Cappadocian sources [Baird et al. 2013]. We tend towards the second version. It should be noted

that contacts between bearers of the Natufian and Karain B cultures were unidirectional. We do not know of any cases of lunates with Helwan retouching in Anatolia.

At the same time, we do not believe that contacts between Natufian and Karain B cultures were of a long-term nature. The spread of long lunates with bipolar retouching was a short-lived episode.

The further development of Late Natufian led to an adaptation of the new technology, when the size of the lunates decreased dramatically. We see this trend in a number of Late Natufian sites, including Rosh Horesha, Rosh Zin, Saflulim and others [Goring-Morris 1987].

It should be noted that there is a view that the onset of contacts between Levantine and Anatolian populations occurred periodically at an earlier date [Erek 2008]. It is possible that such repeated contacts led to the emergence of an information network within which Neolithic innovations later spread.

Distribution of the Karain B culture sites in the western Aegean and on Bosphorus region

Migrations of Karain B culture carriers have been recorded not only to the east, but also to the north. The presence of sites with lunates with bipolar retouching has been documented in the Western Aegean on the Bozburun and Karaburun peninsulas and on the island of Lemnos.

Surface sampling led to the discovery of several sites associated with the Epipaleolithic on the Bozburun peninsula [Atakuman et al. 2020]. Unfortunately, only one site (Hurma) contained a series of 4 lunates and 1 triangle (fig. 15,42-45) with

bipolar retouching. Single platform cores, end and side scrapers, truncations, perforators, and retouched blades were also found at the site.

The Kocaman site on the Karaburun Peninsula has also come to light as a result of surface collections [Çilingiroğlu et al. 2018; 2020]. Single-platform and change-of-orientation cores are present in complex. End- and side scrapers, dihedral and angle burins, backed bladelets, truncations, retouched blades and flakes were found on a site. Two lunates with bipolar retouching were found too (fig. 15,40-41). There are no radiocarbon dates, but the authors compare the Kocaman complex with the Ia1-Ia2 complexes of Öküzini Cave.

Three Epipaleolithic sites have been found on the island of Lemnos. The site of Ouriakos has been excavated [Efstratiou et al. 2014]. Single-platform cores predominate, but opposite-platform cores are also present in the complex. Backed bladelets, end and round scrapers, dihedral and angle burins were found on one site. A large number of geometric microliths are present in the complex, including 114 lunates (fig. 15,46-54) and 1 triangle with bipolar retouching. The site is radiocarbon dated within Drias III (Table 1, 42). The authors synchronise the site with Direkli Cave and the Ia1-Ia2 complexes of Öküzini Cave.

Fig. 16. Fatma-Koba, Layer 5/6. Microliths [Man'ko 2010].

At the same time, the authors emphasise that only 18% of the segments of Öküzini Cave are associated with bipolar retouching, indicating the mixed nature of its complexes.

Agia Marina and Peristereonas are Lemnos sites whose complexes were collected on the surface [Efstratiou et al. 2022]. The authors are convinced that the materials of these sites are different from those of the Ouriakos. The authors of the publication believe that the materials of these lunates differ from those of Ouriakos. The authors write that the lunates of Agia Marina and Peristereonas used abrupt, direct retouching rather than bipolar. This does not seem to be entirely true. Only one lunate, made on a thin plate, has direct retouching on an arc. The other lunates do not differ from the lunates of Ouriakos. Unfortunately, this is not the only mistake made by the authors. The described method of making lunates with bipolar retouching, when the finished microlith is knapped, is absolutely fantastic [Efstratiou et al. 2014, fig. 14]. There is no reason to oppose in any way the methods of lunate production at the Lemnos sites to the methods of lunate production at other Karain B sites.

The determination of the age of the Lemnos sites is based on the use of only one date (Table 1, 42). The date is correct, but this does not mean that the Epipaleolithic of Lemnos did not begin much earlier. It is possible that the Lemnos sites are multilayered.

Three Epipaleolithic sites have been found in the area where the Bosphorus Strait flows into the Black Sea [Gatsov, Özdoğan 1994]. Ağaçlı and Gümüşdere are on the European part of the Black Sea coast, while Domalı is on the Asian part. The material from the sites is associated with surface assemblages. All three sites are similar. Ağaçlı is the most informative complex. There are single-platform, conical and two-platform monofrontal cores. Scrapers are the most numerous in the complex. End scrapers and round and oval scrapers are present. Notched and retouched blade and truncations are not numerous. Microlithic complex is very diverse. I. Gatsov and M. Özdoğan write about such categories of microliths: backed blades with straight backs, backed blades with arched backs, backed pieces. We should not be confused by the lack of reference to lunates with bipolar retouching. Most “backed blades with arched backs” and “backed pieces” are these lunates. Nevertheless, many Ağaçlı

microliths can be described as double-backed points. This circumstance allows us to look for analogues of the Ağaçlı complex in the relatively early Karain B culture complexes. The closest analogue is the eponymous culture complex associated with the Bølling interstadial (Table 1, 5). In general, the Ağaçlı complex shows that the northward migration of the Karain B culture bearers began simultaneously with the geometrization of the complexes in the core area.

Thus, we can see that the process of settlement of Karain B culture bearers begins around the time of the formation of the Layer VIA of Öküzini cave and continues until the Later Dryas. The mapping of the sites gives us an idea of the route of the movement, the sites of the Bozburun and Karaburun peninsulas, the island of Lemnos and the Bosphorus region are marked. We should also note that the northward movement of the carriers of the Karain B culture was connected with the seacoast. This circumstance allows us to assume that the northward movement was associated with a coastal voyage. The presence of obsidian from the Aegean islands at sites on the Karaburun peninsula is an argument in favor of our hypothesis.

Sites with lunates with bipolar retouching in the north-western Black Sea region and the Crimea

The spread of lunates with bipolar retouching has not stopped in the Bosphorus region. The Bilolissya site is known in the northwestern Black Sea region. The site is multi-layered and contains microliths from different archaeological cultures. The presence of two lunates with bipolar retouching is important for us. I. Sapozhnikov links the layer with the lunate finds at Bølling and Allerød [Sapozhnikov 2004].

Many complexes with bipolar retouching are known in Crimea. Skelyasty Grotto (Layers III-2, III-3-A, III-3-X), Shan-Koba (Layers VI, V), Fatma-Koba (Layer 5/6), Vodopadny Grotto are the most informative complexes [Man'ko 2010].

The problem with Crimean Epipaleolithic sites is that most of them are associated with mixed materials. The fact is that two archaeological cultures coexisted in the Crimea during the Late Pleistocene. As a rule, the visits of the representatives of each culture to the sites could not be traced. The first case of interstratification was re-

corded during the excavation of the Skalisty Grotto site, when clean layers with bipolar retouching were found between the layers associated with the Shankobian culture. The new culture is called Taubodrakian.

We will write more about Taubodrakian features using the example of the layer III-3-X Skalisty Grotto complex [Man'ko 2009]. Direct percussion is the main method of blade production. Hard hammers were used in the process of flint knapping. One-platform and two-platform cores with change of orientation predominate. Main classes of tools are end and side scrapers, dihedral and angle burins, burins on truncated faceted blades, blades with retouch and notched blades, perforators. Non-geometric microliths complex contain backed and archbacked blades. Lunates predominate in geometric complex, but trapezes and triangles are present too. Bipolar retouching has been used in both geometric and non-geometric microliths. The geometric complex is associated with a large number of microburins. The Taubodrakian layers have dates within Allerød (Table 1, 43-44).

Complexes with lunates with bipolar retouching from Shan-Koba have dates in the interval from Bølling to Preboreal (Table 1, 45-52). Unfortunately, the mixed nature of the complexes does not allow us to separate the dates associated with the Taubodrakian culture.

The Vodopadny Grotto and Fatma-Koba (Layer 5/6) (fig. 16,1-16) complexes provides us with a set of microliths similar to those known from layer III-3-X of the Skalisty Grotto. We observe the presence of both geometric and non-geometric microliths with bipolar retouching.

As we can see, the Taubodrakian cultural complexes are practically indistinguishable from all the Karain B complexes and even from the complexes in the core area of Antalya. We observe the same methods of stone knapping, the same types of cores, the same typology of tools and the same types of geometric and non-geometric microliths. We also observe the simultaneous existence of the two compared cultures in the period Allerød-Dryas 3. At the same time, we know for sure that the geometrization of the Karain B culture began at least 1-1.5 thousand years before the appearance of the Taubodrakian culture, which suddenly changed the Epigravettian in the

Crimean terrarium. Considering the transport of the Karain B culture to the Bosphorus region, reaching the Crimea was not such a difficult task. We are confident that the comparison of the two cultures fulfils all the criteria described above for the possibility of migration. Thus, we establish the fact that the Taubodrakian culture appeared in Crimea as a result of the migration of carriers of the Karain B culture.

The circle is now complete. The presence of the Taubodrakian culture in the Crimea suggests a further migration of Karain B industry bearers to the east of the Black Sea coast, into the territory of Georgia and north-eastern Turkey. It is possible that this migration is related to the northern route, as Epipalaeolithic complexes with lunates with bipolar retouching are not currently known in the southern Black Sea region.

Conclusion

We have examined most of the published and studied complexes with lunates with bipolar retouching and can draw the following conclusions:

1. The stone industry in Antalya was formed in the Bølling Interstadial and developed until the end of the Pleistocene or even before the Preboreal.
2. The movement eastwards from the core area in Antalya took place throughout the existence of the Karain B culture. This movement led to the establishment of contacts with the bearers of the Natufian culture. This contact was made possible by the sharing of obsidian deposits in eastern Cappadocia.
3. The relationship between the Karain B and Natufian cultures can be characterised as a unidirectional cultural influence. The contact between the two cultures resulted in the appearance of a new type of microliths, which completely replaced the Helwan-retouched lunates previously produced by the carriers of Natufian culture. The reverse influence on the carriers of the Karain B culture was not recorded.
4. The mapping of the northward movement of Karain B carriers shows the migration route through the eastern Aegean coast to the Bosphorus Strait, as well as their further advance into Crimea and the eastern Black Sea region.
5. Analysis of the Black Sea sites, comparing their complexes with those of the Karain B cul-

ture, shows their absolute similarity. Radiocarbon dates indicate a later age of the Black Sea monuments compared to the oldest dates of the Antalya complexes. This circumstance allows us to infer a large-scale migration of the bearers of the Karain B culture.

6. The migration of the carriers of the Karain B culture could be related to seafaring, as all the sites with lunates with bipolar retouching are either in the immediate vicinity or at a short distance from the shores of the Aegean and Black Seas. Absolute proof of the practice of seafaring is the presence of obsidian from the islands of the Aegean coastal sites.

7. The movement of the carriers of the Karain B culture led to the creation of a vast network based on common origin or cultural contacts, as in the case of the Natufian culture. The creation of such a network in the pre-Neolithic period played an important role in the further spread of Neolithic innovations in the Early Holocene.

The data from the natural sciences are corroborated to some extent by our conclusions. The study of the cemeteries of Pınarbaşı (Table 1, 12-13) and

Satsurblia (Table 1, 53) showed a genetic similarity of the buried people. The burial at Pınarbaşı shows the presence of mitDNA K2b [Feldman 2020]. The burial from Satsurblia has a sister mitDNA K3 [Jones et al. 2015]. These data, obtained at the extremes of the described network, show that population movements took place.

Further study of the giant network described will make it possible to study the mechanisms of the creation of such global information systems of the Epipaleolithic and their role in the process of neolithization.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank the Ministry of Culture and Tourism – Turkey for the permission of the Trabzon Survey Project (Project No. YA016101(2018)).

Funding

This work was supported by the Scientific Research Projects Coordination Unit of Karadeniz Technical University (Project No. SAT-2020-8417) and TÜBİTAK (Project No. 220K415).

Bibliography

- Albrecht 1988:** G. Albrecht, Preliminary Results of the Excavation in the Karain B Cave Near Antalya/Turkey: The Upper Paleolithic Assemblages and the Upper Pleistocene Climatic Development. *Paleorient*:14, No 2, 1988, 211-222.
- Atakuman et al. 2022:** Ç. Atakuman, B. Erdoğan, H. C. Gemici, I. Baykara, M. Karakoç, P. Biagi, E. Starnini, D. Guilbeau, N. Yücel, D. Turan, M. Dirican, Before the Neolithic in the Aegean: The Pleistocene and the Early Holocene record of Bozburun - Southwest Turkey. *The Journal of Island and Coastal Archaeology*. Volume 17, Issue 3, 2022, 1-33.
- Baird 2012:** D. Baird, Pınarbaşı, 1; from Epipaleolithic campsite to sedentarising village in central Anatolia. Pp. 181–218 in M. Özdoğan and N. Başgelen (eds), *Neolithic in Turkey; New Excavations, New Discoveries* (Istanbul 2012).
- Baird et al. 2013:** D. Baird, E. Asouti, L. Astruc, A. Baysal, E.L. Baysal, D. Carruthers, A.S. Fairbairn, C. Kabukcu, E. Jenkins, K.O. Lorentz, C. Middleton, J.A. Pearson, A. Pirie, Juniper smoke, skulls and wolves' tails. The Epipaleolithic of the Anatolian plateau in its South-west Asian context; insights from Pınarbaşı, 1. *Levant* 45 (2), 2013, 175-209.
- Bar-Yosef et al. 2011:** O. Bar-Yosef, Belfer-Cohen, T. Mesheviliani, N. Jakeli, G. Bar-Oz, E. Boaretto, P. Goldberg, E. Kvavadze, Z. Matskevich, Dzudzuana: an Upper Palaeolithic cave site in the Caucasus foothills (Georgia). *Antiquity* 85, 2011, 331-49.
- Bayon et al. 2002:** I.L. Bayon, J.M. Leotard, M. Kartal, La grotte d'Okuzini: chronologie et mode de fonctionnement d'un remplissage (analyse radiométrique, rythme sédimentaire et cycles climatiques). In: Otte M. (ed.). *Okuzini: Final Palaeolithic evolution in Southwest Anatolia*. ERAUL 96, 2002, 49-74.
- Benecke 2006:** N. Benecke, Zur Datierung der Faunensequenz am Abri San-Koba (Krim, Ukraine). *Beiträge zur Archäozoologie und Prahistorischen Anthropologie* (5), 2006, 12-15.
- Biagi et al. 2014:** P. Biagi, G.A. Khlopachev, D.V. Kiosak, The radiocarbon chronology of Shan-Koba rock-shelter, a Late Palaeolithic and Mesolithic sequence in the Crimean Mountains (Ukraine). *Diadora* (28), 2014, 7-20.
- Bostancı 1959:** E.Y. Bostancı, Research on the Mediterranean Coast of Anatolia. A New Paleolithic Site at Beldibi Near Antalya, *Anadolu (Anatolia)*, Sayı 4, 1959, 129-178.

- Bostancı 1962:** E.Y. Bostancı, Belbaşı Kaya Sığınağında Bulunan Üst Paleolitik ve Mezolitik Endüstri”, Belleten, XXVI.Cilt, Sayı 102, 1962, 233-292.
- Byrd 1988:** B.F. Byrd, Late Pleistocene Settlement Diversity in the Azraq Basin. *Paléorient* 14/2, 1988, 257-264.
- Cohen et al. 1996:** V. Cohen, N. Gerasimenko, L. Rekovetz, A. Starkin, 1996. Chronostratigraphie of Rockchelter Skalisty: implementations for the Late Glacial of Crimea. *Prehistoire Europeene* (9), 1996, 326-356.
- Conard 2002:** N.J. Conard, An Overview of the Excavations at Baaz Rockshelter, Damascus Province, Syria. In: Aslan et al. (eds.) 2002, *Festschrift für Manfred Korfmann.*, Mauerschau 2, 2002, 623-640.
- Çalışkan Akgül 2016:** H. Çalışkan Akgül, Türkiye'nin Doğu Karadeniz Bölgesi'nin Prehistoryası: Bir Terra Incognita Analizi. *Karadeniz İncelemeleri Dergisi* 21, 2016, 9-26. <https://doi.org/10.18220/kid.277658>.
- Çalışkan Akgül, Dinçer 2021:** H. Çalışkan Akgül, B. Dinçer, Koskarlı Cave: The first Late Pleistocene/Early Holocene site in the eastern Black Sea region of Turkey. *Archaeological Research in Asia* Volume 27, 2021.
- Çilingiroğlu et al. 2018:** Ç. Çilingiroğlu, B. Dinçer, I. Baykara, A. Uhri, C. Çakırlar. A possible Late Pleistocene forager site from the Karaburun Peninsula, western Turkey. *Antiquity* Volume 92 Issue 362, 2018, 1-5
- Çilingiroğlu et al. 2020:** Ç. Çilingiroğlu, M. Kaczanowska, J.K. Kozłowski, B. Dincer, C. Cakırlar, D. Turan. Between Anatolia and the Aegean: Epipalaeolithic and Mesolithic Foragers of the Karaburun Peninsula. *Journal of Field Archaeology*, 45(7), 2020, 479-497.
- Efstratiou et al. 2014:** N. Efstratiou, P. Biagi, E. Starnini, The Epipalaeolithic site of Ouriakos on the island of Lemnos and its place in the Late Pleistocene peopling of the East Mediterranean region. *Adalya*, 17, 2014, 1-24.
- Efstratiou et al. 2022:** N. Efstratiou, P. Biagi, E. Starnini, D. Kyriakou, A. Eleftheriadou, Agia Marina and Peristerernas: Two New Epipalaeolithic Sites on the Island of Lemnos (Greece). *Journal of Paleolithic Archaeology*, 5:5, 2022, 1-34. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41982-022-00118-8>
- Erdoğu et al. 2003:** B. Erdoğu, O. Tanındı, D. Uygun, The 14C Database of Archaeological Settlements in Turkey. TAY (Istanbul 2003)
- Erek 2008:** C.M. Erek, Levant-ic anadolu arasindaki prehistoric baglantilarda amik-maras cokuntu alaninin onemi (Yeni Buluntular Işığında Amik-Maraş Çöküntü Alanının Levant-İç Anadolu Arasındaki Prehistorik Bağlantılara Katkıları). *OLBA*, XVI, 2008, 1-22.
- Erek 2010:** C.M. Erek, A New Epi-Palaeolithic Site in the Northeast Mediterranean Region. *Adalya* XIII, 2010, 1-17.
- Feldman 2020:** M. Feldman, Tracing past human mobility and disease in western Eurasia by the genetic analysis of ancient human remains (Jena 2020)
- Gatsov, Özdoğan 1994:** I. Gatsov, M. Özdoğan, Some Epipalaeolithic sites from NW Turkey. *Agakli, Domali and Gumusdere. Anatolica* 20, 1994, 97-120.
- Gattinger et al. 1962:** T.E. Gattinger, C. Erentöz, I. Ketin, 1:500.000 Ölçekli Türkiye Jeoloji Haritası. Trabzon. MTA Yayınları (Ankara 1962).
- Gerasimenko 1997:** N.P. Gerasimenko, Prirodnaia sreda obitaniia cheloveka na iugo-vostoke Ukrainy v pozdnelednikov'e i golocene (po materialam paleogeograficheskogo izuchenija arheologicheskikh pamiatnikov). *Arheologicheskii al'manah*, № 6, 1997, 3-64 // Н.П. Герасименко, Природная среда обитания человека на юго-востоке Украины в позднеледниковье и голоцене (по материалам палеогеографического изучения археологических памятников). *Археологический альманах*, № 6, 1997, 3-64.
- Grigolia 1977:** G.K. Grigolia, Neolithic of Central Colchis Paluri (Tbilisi 1977).
- Golovanova, Doronichev 2012:** L.V. Golovanova, V.B. Doronichev, Imeretinskaia kul'tura v vekhnem paleolite Kavkaza: proshloe i nastoiashchee. V: Sinitsyna G.V., Fediunin I.V. (sost.). *Pervobytnye drevnosti Evrazii. K 60-letiiu A. Sorokina. Moskva: IA RAN*, 2012, 59-102 // Л.В. Голованова, В.Б. Дороничев. Имеретинская культура в верхнем палеолите Кавказа: прошлое и настоящее. В: Синицына Г.В., Федюнин И.В. (сост.). *Первобытные древности Евразии. К 60-летию А. Сорокина. Москва: ИА РАН*, 2012, 59-102.
- Goring-Morris 1987:** A. N. Goring-Morris, At the Edge. Terminal Pleistocene Hunter-Gatherers in the Negev and Sinai, *BAR International* (Oxford 1987).
- Grosman et al. 2016:** L. Grosman, N.D. Munro, I. Abadi, E. Boaretto, D. Shaham, A. Belfer-Cohen, O. Bar-Yosef, Nahal Ein Gev II, a Late Natufian community at the Sea of Galilee. *PLoS ONE* 11, 2016, 1-32.
- Güven 1998:** I.H. Güven, 1/100000 Ölçekli Açınsama Nitelikli Türkiye Jeoloji Haritaları. *Maden Tetkik ve Arama Genel Müdürlüğü*, No: 59, 1998, Ankara.
- Henry 1973:** D.O. Henry, The Natufian Site of Rosh Zin: A Preliminary Report. *Palestine Exploration Quarterly*. Volume 105, Issue 2, 1973, 129-140.
- Housley 1994:** R.A. Housley, Eastern Mediterranean Chronologies: The Oxford AMS Contribution. *Radiocarbon* 36, 1994, 55-73.

- Jones et al. 2016:** E.R. Jones, G. Gonzalez-Fortes, S. Connell, V. Siska, A. Eriksson, R. Martiniano, R.L. McLaughlin, M. Gallego-Llorente, L.M. Cassidy, C. Gamba, T. Meshveliani, O. Bar-Yosef, W. Müller, A. Belfer-Cohen, Z. Mat-skevich, N. Jakeli, T.F. Higham, M. Currat, D. Lordkipanidze, M. Hofreiter, A. Manica, R. Pinhasi, D. G. Bradley. Upper Palaeolithic genomes reveal deep roots of modern Eurasians. *National Commun* 6, 2016, 8912 doi: 10.1038/ncomms9912.
- Kartal 2003:** M. Kartal, Anatolian Epi-Paleolithic Period Assemblages. *Anatolia* 24, 2003, 45-62.
- Kartal 2017:** G. Kartal, Yüzey Buluntuları Işığında Kızılın Yontmataş Endüstrisinin Tekno-Tipolojisi. *DTCF Der-gisi* 59.1 (2019): 2017, 398-427
- Kartal 2018:** G. Kartal, The Neolithic Cave Settlements of the Antalya Region in Southwestern Anatolia: A Com-parative Perspective in Terms of Chipped Stone Assemblages. *ADALYA* 21, 2018, 1-18.
- Klein 1999:** L.S. Klein, Migratsia: arheologicheskie priznaki. *Stratum plus*, 1, 1999, 52-71 // Л.С. Клейн, Мигра-ция: археологические признаки. *Stratum plus*, 1, 1999, 52-71.
- Kovalchuk et al. 2021:** O. Kovalchuk, L. Rekovets, A. Tsvelykh, V. Yanenko, V. Manko, S. Tajkova, Living in a time of change: Late Pleistocene/ Holocene transitional vertebrate fauna of Grot Skeliastyi (Crimea, Ukraine), *Historical Biology*, 2021, 33:10, 2074-2084.
- Kozłowski, Kaczanowska 2004:** J. K., Kozłowski, M. Kaczanowska, Gravettian/Epigravettian sequences in Balkans and Anatolia. *Mediterranean Archaeology and Archaeometry*, Vol. 4, 1, 2004, 5-18.
- Larson, Marks 1977:** P.A. Larson, A.E. Marks, Test Excavations at the Natufian Site of Rosh Horesha. In: Marks (ed.) 1977, Prehistory and Paleoenvironments in the Central Negev, Israel, Volume II: The Avdat/Aqev Area, Part 2 and the Har Harif, Dallas, 1977, 191-232.
- Leotard, Bayon 2006:** J.M. Leotard, I.L. Bayon, La Grotte d'Okuzini: etude de materiel lithique. In: Ed. Otte M. Okuzini: Final Paleolithic evolution in Southeast Anatolia. *ERAUL* 96. Liege: Universite de Liege, 2006, 109-234.
- Man'ko 2009:** V.O. Man'ko, Tipologichna variabelnist' kompleksiv geometrichnikh mikrolitiv tret'oi pachki shariv stoianki Grot Skeliastii. *Arheologicheskii al'manakh*, 20, 2009, 247-268 // В.О. Манько, Типологічна варіабель-ність комплексів геометричних мікролітів третьої пачки шарів стоянки Грот Скалистый. *Археологический альманах*, 20, 2009, 247-268.
- Man'ko 2010:** V. A. Man'ko, Sluchai interstratifikatsii v sloiakh pachki 3 stoianki Grot Skalisty i vopros o proisho-jdenii krymskogo final'nogo paleoita. *Stratum plus*, 1, 2010, 245-262 // В.А. Манько, Случаи интерстратифика-ции в слоях пачки 3 стоянки Грот Скалистый и вопрос о происхождении крымского финального палеоита. *Stratum plus*, 1, 2010, 245-262
- Man'ko 2013:** V. O. Man'ko, Final'nyi paleolit – neolit Krimu (Київ 2013) // В.О. Манько, Фінальний палеоліт – неоліт Криму (Київ 2013).
- Marks 1976:** A. Marks, Glossary. In: Prehistory and Paleoenvironments in the Central Negev, Israel, edited by An-thony Marks. Vol. 1: The Avdat/ Aqev Area, Part 1 (Dallas 1976).
- Nebieridze 1972:** L. Nebieridze, The Neolithic of Western Transcaucasia (Tbilisi 1972).
- Neeley 2010:** M.P. Neeley, TBAS 102: A Late Natufian Site in West-Central Jordan. *Neo-Lithic*, 1/10, 2010, 86-91.
- Nioradze, Otte 2000:** M. Nioradze, M. Otte, Paléolithique supérieur de Géorgie. *L'Anthropologie* 104, 2000, 265-300.
- Nishiaki et al. 2017:** Y. Nishiaki, M. Yoneda, Y. Kanjou, T. Akazawa, Natufian in the north: The Late Epipalaeolithic cultural entity at Dederiyeh Cave, northwest Syria. *Paléorient* 43(2): 2017, 7-24.
- Sapozhnikov 2004:** I.V. Sapozhnikov, Mnogoslojnaja stojanka Mihajlovka (Beloles'e): problemy stratigrafii i dati-rovki. *Starojitnosti Pivnichnogo Prichornomor'ia i Krimu*. Т. XI, 2004, 299-313 // И.В. Сапожников, Многослой-ная стоянка Михайловка (Белолесье): проблемы стратиграфии и датировки. *Старожитності Північного Причорномор'я і Криму*. Т. XI, 2004, 299-313.
- Sapozhnikov, Sapozhnikova 2011:** I.V. Sapozhnikov, G.V. Sapozhnikova. Kamennyi vek Severo-Zapadnogo Prichornomor'ia. *Stratum plus*, 1, 2011, 15-149 // И.В. Сапожников, Г.В. Сапожникова, Каменный век Северо-Западного Причерноморья. *Stratum plus*, 1, 2011, 15-149.
- Stutz 2004:** A.J. Stutz, The natufian in real time? Radiocarbon date calibration as a tool for understanding natufian societies and their long-term prehistoric context, *The Last Hunter-Gatherer Societies in the Near East*, ed. C. De-lage. Oxford: John and Erica Hedges (BAR International Series, 1320), 2004, 11-37.
- Taşkıran et al. 2017:** H. Taşkıran, K. Özçelik, G. Kartal, Y. Aydın, B. Findık, H. Bulut, E. Erbil, M.B. Kösem, 2015 Yılı Karain Mağarası Kazıları, 38. Kazı Sonuçları Toplantısı, Cilt 1, 2017, 521-538.
- Yalçınkaya et al. 2014:** I. Yalçınkaya, H. Taşkıran, M. Kartal, K. Özçelik, M.B. Kösem, G. Kartal, Y. Aydın, M. Karakoç, B. Findık, E. Erbil. „2013 Yılı Karain Mağarası Kazıları, 36. Kazı Sonuçları Toplantısı, Cilt 1, 2014, 441-458

Hülya Çalışkan Akgül, PhD, Karadeniz Technical University, e-mail: hulyaakgul@ktu.edu.tr
ORCID: 0000-0002-6619-9898

Valery Man'ko, PhD, Institute of Archeology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, e-mail: valery_manko@yahoo.com
ORCID: 0000-0002-2990-7234

Didem Turan, MA, Karadeniz Technical University, e-mail: didemturan@ktu.edu.tr
ORCID: 0000-0001-8375-1296

Guram Chkhatarashvili, PhD, Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University, e-mail: guramchkhatarashvili@bsu.edu.ge
ORCID: 0000-0002-0568-9797

Sinan Kılıç, PhD, Van Yüzüncü Yıl University, e-mail: sinankilic@yyu.edu.tr
ORCID: 0000-0003-3424-4081